

APPENDIX 5 - PROFESSIONAL PROFILE QUESTIONNAIRE

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PART 1 - ACADEMIC BACKGROUND

1) What is your educational background?

- Bachelor's Degree in Computer Science
- Bachelor's Degree in Software Engineering
- Bachelor's Degree in Computer Engineering
- Bachelor's Degree in Information Systems
- Bachelor's Degree in Artificial Intelligence
- Other _____

2) What is your level of education?

- up to 4 semesters
- 5 to 8 semesters
- 9 to 12 semesters
- more than 12 semesters

PART 2 - PROJECT IDENTIFICATION AND FUNCTION

3) What is your main role or function in the Software Factory?

- Requirements Analyst
- Developer
- Tester
- Scrum Master / Product Owner
- Other

4) How long have you been working at the Software Factory of the Institute of Informatics?

- Less than 6 months
- 6 months to 1 year
- 1 to 3 years
- More than 3 years

5) How many projects have you participated in within the Software Factory?

- 1 to 2
- 3 to 5
- More than 5

PART 3 - PREVIOUS EXPERIENCE WITH REQUIREMENTS ENGINEERING AND PRIVACY

6) How would you rate your practical ability in the main activities of the Requirements Engineering process?

	None	Little	Median	Many	Specialist
Elicitation or collection					
Analysis and modeling					
Specification/documentation					
Verification and validation					
Management					

7) Have you ever used standards catalogs or best practice repositories in software projects?

- Microsoft Word and Excel or similar
- Jira / Trello / ClickUp
- GitHub / GitLab
- Modeling (Draw.io, Figma, Enterprise Architect...)
- Other:

8) How often do Software Factory projects require addressing personal data privacy requirements?

- 1 - Never
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5 - Always

9) How would you rate your practical skills regarding personal data privacy requirements?

- 1 - No practical skills with privacy requirements.
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5 - Specialist in handling privacy requirements.

10) How would you rate your theoretical knowledge of the General Data Protection Law (LGPD), Law No. 13.709/2018?

- 1 - No theoretical knowledge
- 2

- 3
- 4
- 5 - Specialist

11) Como você avalia a sua habilidade prática em tratar requisitos de privacidade de dados pessoais em conformidade com a LGPD?

- 1 - No practical skills in applying the LGPD (Brazilian General Data Protection Law).
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5 - Specialist in applying the LGPD (Brazilian General Data Protection Law).

12) Do you believe that CPRP integrates well with the current tools and workflows of the Software Factory?

- Checklist.
- Guide.
- Taxonomy.
- Catalog of privacy requirements standards.
- Software tool.
- I have never used supporting artifacts.
- Other.